

Influence of Promotional Strategies and Women's Awareness on the Buying Behaviour of Organic Cosmetic Products

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Abstract: There is a tremendous growth in personal care and cosmetics industry. India is rich in the production of cosmetic products and is able to withstand in the global market. Cosmetic products are much needed by young women in India. Women are well educated and they do not have time to prepare herbal products at home but depend on branded products which are available in the market. In the present study, an attempt has been made to find out the purchasing habit and the impact of advertisement of organic cosmetic products towards purchasing behaviour and to examine the harmful effects on environment consciousness, skin safety, appearance, and by word of mouth which will influence the consumers' attitude towards organic cosmetic products in India. Hypothesis have been framed to find out the association between age, occupation and promotion media and to find out whether environmental awareness, skin safety awareness, awareness about appearance, towards their attitude in buying organic cosmetic products with the help of relevant statistical tools and valid conclusion has been arrived at. Primary data has been collected from 150 women in Madurai District and analysed with the help of Chi-square test, ANOVA and regression analysis. Secondary data has been collected from Books, journals, web resources from both published and unpublished sources.

Keywords: Organic, Cosmetic products, consumers' attitude, organic products, promotion media, awareness.

JEL Classification Number: M3

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1.Introduction

Natural ingredients have always been a part of the beauty care cosmetic products in India. The packs may be, 'milk-honey, basin-milk cream, turmeric-milk, Green gram-milk pack are used apply as face pack on the face of women to make it as a glowing skin. Since women are going for jobs, they do not have time to prepare the face packs at home and they purchase instant solutions for them beauty needs as they are aware of the harmful effects of chemical based products and they go in to buying organic cosmetic products. India occupies 1% of the total share of the global organic skin products and in the next 5 years, the share on anticipated to increase tremendously. This on due to disposable income, young women privileged population and rising middle class populations. Cosmetics and personal care industry grows very fast and it offer huge growth potential to foreign companies. This is due to increase in the number of working women change in their lifestyle, affordability to buy luxury products by modern working women.

Women in India are conscious of their skin, in colour, to look bright, reduction of wrinkles and there is great demand for skin care product. Indian companies such as, Patanjali, Himalaya, Dabur, Emami , Biotique, VLCC, Lotus, Jovees, Kama ayurveda, etc are selling cosmetic product with organic base such us anti-aging properties, moisturising care and sun tan protection's which are popular among Indian women. There is high demand for organic cosmetic in the age group of below 30 years. International companies are investing huge amount of money in research and development to produce products which are less harmful to health. Indian consumers prefer to buy natural/herbal branded cosmetic products. India is the second largest exporter of herbal cosmetics to the world market next to china. India exports to countries like, UAE, USA, NETHORLAND, SAUDI ARABIA, GERMANY, JAPAN, MALASIA, NEPAL, SRI LANKA, U.K, CHINA, INDONESIA, FRANCE, RUSSIA and ITALY. Efforts are being taken to promote Ayurvedic products along with Ministry of health and family welfare and are exposed and accounts for 1% of the market in India.

1.1 Consumer interest in buying organic cosmetic products:

The customers who are using chemical cosmetics suffer due to skin problems and they considered as unsafe to use these products. As a result, they switch over to natural cosmetics products which are free from chemicals. As the ingredients for production of cosmetic products are Ayurvedic or herbal in nature, they considered those as safe by the consumers. The customers prefer organic products because the environment in cities is highly polluted and they are afraid that this will result in health related problems. The factors affecting organic cosmetic industry are, increasing in the concern for beauty care, increasing health awareness, efforts from operating companies, increase in the disposable

income of an individual, improvement in the standard of living, short span of life shelf value of organic cosmetics, advanced beauty treatments and Government regulation and support.

2. Literature Review

The following is the review of literature relating to the present study. Sekar, Ramya (2017) the study reveals that most of the respondents are aware about Himalaya Ayurvedic products. Now a day's people are considering the cosmetics are not only for luxury but also consider for improving health condition. Himalaya ayurvedic manufacturing company is a leading company to introduce best brand. The company has got a good name and same for its quality and innovative products to satisfy the current demand for their customer.

Abhinav Kataria (2018) Ayurvedic or the 'science longevity' is the system of nature cure. Ayurvedic [Ayur + Veda] is considered to be a sub-Veda or the branch of knowledge that is concerned with the physical health and happiness on earth which therefore assumes great significance to human life. This is an indication to the age old roots of Ayurveda. Ancient physicians segmented the universe into different types of manifested energy and attributed the very same energy to food and herbs. Patanjali is the leading producer of Ayurveda based products, and it is the only company to directly challenge the industry incumbents in India, such as Unilever, Dabur, P&G, Marico, and Nestle.

Anitha, Ruba (2018) Living healthy is the wish of each and every human being in the world. Recently there is much news which is not positive with regard to the products that we use both internally and externally. The study reveals that majority of the consumers are satisfied with the Patanjali products and the variables namely marital status, period of usage, amount spent, and suggestion to purchase are associated with the level of satisfaction on Patanjali products.

RadhaKrishnan, Radhika.k (2018) this study is concerned with the analysis of "Customer Satisfaction towards Himalaya products in Cuddalore Town". In a survey method of study conducted among 100 sample respondents in order to analyses the customer satisfaction towards quality, price and quantity consumption of Himalaya product. Many of them consume the Himalaya product because of it's an herbal product and also it has good quality. All people know about Himalaya product but price discount must be said that in television then it has varieties of product but more than that the customers know about the baby skin care. So the producer should understand what is exactly expected from him by the consumers because it facilitates to increase the sale much.

Sabahat Shakeel (2019) In a study on, Consumer Buying Behaviour towards Organic Cosmetics versus Non-Organic Cosmetics the researcher has analysed the factor which

changes the consumer buying behaviour. Primary data has been collected for the study and the result of this research has been found that consumers are showing more interest to purchase an organic product than the non-organic cosmetic products.

Dr.Reena Malik et.al, (2020) the researcher has done a study on consumer attitude towards organic cosmetic products, the researcher explained about the awareness about the organic product and also to determine the consciousness of the consumer about the organic cosmetic product. The study revealed that the consumer awareness, skin awareness towards organic cosmetic products has changed the attitude of the consumer towards organic cosmetic products.

Sidra Ishaq (2021) in this study, the researcher has discussed about the factors which influence female purchase behavior for buying organic cosmetic products, and the consumer buying behaviour towards organic cosmetic products. Consumers thoughts are associated with environmental and health benefits. The result of the study shows that the consumers are more conscious about the products which are used for their skin care, thus the consumer thought differs from other products than the cosmetic products.

Based on the literature survey, the following objectives have been framed.

3. Objectives of the study

The following are the objectives of the present study.

1. To find out the demographic profile of the women respondents in the study area.
2. To find out the purchasing habit and the impact of promotion methods of organic cosmetic products towards buying behaviour and
3. To analyse the awareness among the respondents towards purchase of organic cosmetic products.

4. Framework of Hypotheses

The following hypotheses have been framed :

H01. There is no significant association between age and promotion methods of Organic cosmetic products.

H02. There is no significant association between occupation and promotion methods of Organic cosmetic products.

H03: There is no significant association between income and brand loyalty towards purchase of Organic cosmetic products.

H04. Environmental awareness will positively influence attitude toward buying organic cosmetics.

H05: Skin safety awareness will positively influence attitude toward buying organic cosmetics.

H06: Appearance awareness will positively influence attitude toward buying organic cosmetics.

H07: Word of mouth will positively influence attitude toward buying organic cosmetics.

5. Methodology

Primary Data has been collected from 150 women respondents living in and around Madurai District of Tamilnadu by means of a self-administered questionnaire survey. Primary data has been collected and analysed with the help of Chi-square test, ANOVA and regression analysis. Secondary data has been collected from Books, journals, web resources from both published and unpublished sources.

6.Data analysis

Demographic profile of the respondents

TABLE 1 : Age-Wise Classification

S.No.	Age group (years)	No. of Respondents	Percentage
01	Less than 20	48	32.00
02	20-30	34	22.67
03	30-40	23	15.33
04	40-50	31	20.67
05	More than 50	14	9.33
Total		150	100.00

Table 1 explains the age - wise classification of the respondents. It clearly shows out of 150 respondents 32 per cent of the respondents belong to the age group of less than 20 years. Nearly 23 per cent of the respondents fall under the age group of 20 – 30 years. The respondents 40 -50 years of age constitute 20.67 per cent of the total respondent. The senior respondents are more than 50 years of age who are accounted for 9.33 per cent of the total. It shows that the senior people are less interested in using organic cosmetic products and youngsters have the habit of using cosmetic products more than that of others.

Sources of Brand awareness

TABLE 2 : Sources of Brand Awareness

S.No.	Source	No. of respondents	Percentage
01	Sales representative	16	10.67
02	Advertisement media	55	36.67
03	Social media	27	18.00
04	Publicity	22	14.67
05	Sales promotion methods	30	20.00
Total		150	100.00

Table 2 reveals that out of 150 sample respondents, majority of the respondents became aware of the cosmetic brand through advertisements which alone accounts for about 36 per cent. In the next place, 20 per cent of the respondents know their brands through sales promotion methods. The respondents, who know about the brands through friends and relatives, account for nearly 18 per cent of total respondents. Publicity influences the respondents to some extent, because about 15 per cent of the respondents get awareness of the brands through publicity. It is understood from the table that advertisement plays a vital role to make aware of the respondents about different cosmetic brands.

Point Of Purchase

The place of purchase of cosmetic by the consumers is important from the stand viewpoint of the producer of the cosmetic product, because they may apply intensive sales promotion technique to that particular point to increase sales. Table 4 gives the different point of purchase of the respondents.

TABLE 3 : Points Of Purchase

S.No.	Point of Purchase	No.of respondents	Percentage
01	Departmental store	79	52.67
02	General merchant	43	28.67
03	Beauty parlour	9	6.00
04	Grocery	19	12.66
Total		150	100.00

It is clear from the table 3 that the majority (52.67%) of the respondents purchased the cosmetic product from the Department store followed by 28.67 per cent of respondents purchased from General Merchant. Another 12.66 per cent of the respondents make their sales promotion technique at departmental stores .

Effective Promotion Media And Age Wise Classification

The opinion of the respondents about effective sales promotion media and age wise classification of the respondents is given in table 4.

H01. There is no significant association between age and promotion methods of cosmetic organic products. The hypothesis has been tested with the help of ANOVA tool and the findings are given as under.

TABLE 4 : Effective Promotion Media And Age Wise Classification

Age of respondents	Sales Promotion media					Total
	Press Media	Radio	Television	Cinema	Wall Advertisement	
Less than 20	4	6	32	3	3	48
20 – 30	3	3	22	2	4	34
30 – 40	4	5	10	2	2	23
40 – 50	2	7	16	3	3	31
More than 40	7	2	2	1	2	14
Total	20	23	82	11	14	150

Table 4 shows that the most of the respondents irrespective of age are of the opinion that television media is most effective than others. Therefore, it is necessary to examine whether there is significant difference between opinion of the respondents about sales promotion media and the age of the respondents.

TABLE 4.1 : ANOVA Table

Source of Variation	Sum of Squares(SS)	Degrees of Freedom	Mean Square	F ratio	Table value	Level of @ 5%
Between Samples	694	4	173.5	$\frac{173.5}{28} = 6.196$	2.8661	Significant
With in Samples	560	20	28.00			

Result :

Since the table value is less than the calculated value, the null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, it is concluded that there is a significant difference between opinion of the respondents about sales promotion media and the age of the respondents.

Effective Promotion Method And Occupation Of The Respondents

The following table 5 shows the various promotion methods to sell organic cosmetic products based on their occupation. The following hypothesis has been framed and tested with the help of ANOVA and the results are shown as under.

HO2. There is no significant association between occupation and promotion methods of cosmetic organic products.

TABLE 5 : Effective Promotion Method And Occupation Of The Respondents

Occupation	Promotion Method				Total
	Advertisement	Sales promotion	Publicity	Personal selling	
Students	15	3	3	2	23
Business	7	6	2	1	16
Profession	16	4	5	2	27
Employment	15	9	5	3	32
Farmers	5	2	1	1	9
Housewives	29	6	5	3	43
Total	87	30	21	12	150

Table 5 shows the most of the respondents are of the opinion that the advertisement is the most effective promotion methods irrespective of occupation. So, it is necessary to analyze whether there is any significant difference between opinion of the respondents about effective promotion methods and occupation of the respondents.

The opinion of the respondents about the effective promotion method is verified and tested with help of one-way ANOVA.

TABLE 5.1 : ANOVA Table

Source of Variation	Sum of Squares(SS)	Degrees of Freedom	Mean Square	F ratio	Table value	Level of @ 5%
Between Samples	571.5	3	190.5	190.5/20.55= 9.270	3.098	Significant
With in Samples	411	20	20.55			

Result :

Since the table value is less than the calculated value, the null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, it may be concluded that there is a significant difference between opinion of the respondents about promotion methods and occupation of the respondents.

Opinion About Advertisement

Advertising is that activity by which visual or oral messages are addressed to the general public. Its purpose is to inform or influence them in order to increase the sales of the advertiser. It is done with a view to sell the goods or services, offered by the advertiser. It may also draw the readers or viewers to act favourably towards the idea or institutions featured. The aim is to persuade people to buy more. Advertising creates desire for new products. The success of advertising greatly depends upon effective advertising programme. Therefore it is necessary to analyze the opinion of the respondents about the advertisement. It is presented in the table 7.

The following table 6 shows the brand loyalty of the consumers towards purchase of organic cosmetic products based on their income. The following hypothesis has been framed and tested with the help of Chi-square test and the results are shown as under.

H03: There is no significant association between income and brand loyalty towards purchase of cosmetic organic products.

TABLE 6 : Brand Loyalty and Income Wise Classification

Monthly Income	Brand Loyalty		Total
	Willing to change	Not willing to change	
Less than 10,000	28	23	51
10,000 – 20,000	23	18	41
20,000 – 30,000	21	22	43
More than 30,000	11	4	15
Total	83	67	150

Source: Primary data.

TABLE 6.1 : CHI-SQUARE Test T Result

Table Value	Calculated Value	Level of @ 5%
3.84	2.71	Not Significant

Result :

As the calculated value is less than the table value, the Null hypothesis is accepted. So it is proved that there is no significant difference between opinion of the respondents about brand loyalty and income of the respondents.

Hypotheses Testing to realise the third objective, the following are the findings

To realise the third objective namely, to analyse the awareness among the respondents towards purchase of organic cosmetic products the following hypotheses namely,

H04: Environmental awareness will positively influence attitude toward buying organic cosmetics.

H05: Skin safety awareness will positively influence attitude toward buying organic cosmetics.

H06: Appearance awareness will positively influence attitude toward buying organic cosmetics.

H07: Word of mouth will positively influence attitude toward buying organic cosmetics.

To test the reliability of data, the Cronbach Alpha was calculated for the variables such as, environmental awareness, skin safety awareness, appearance awareness and word of mouth has been done.

Table -7 : Table showing the value of the variables .

Variables	Cronbach Alpha Value	Mean	Standard deviation
Environmental Awareness	0.730	4.11	0.449
Skin Safety Awareness	0.927	3.41	0.690
Appearance Awareness	0.737	2.23	0.613
Word of Mouth (interpersonal communication)	0.7	4.22	0.884

Source: Primary Data

For the above four variables, reliabilities were 0.730 for environmental awareness scale with a mean of 4.11 and standard deviation of 0.449, and 0.927 for skin safety awareness scale with a mean of 3.41 and standard deviation of 0.690, 0.737 for appearance awareness

scale with a mean of 2.23 and standard deviation of 0.613, and word of mouth (interpersonal awareness) with a mean of 4.22 and standard deviation of 0.884. The alpha values found for the scales were all above 0.7.

Linear regression was run for each factor to test the hypotheses with the purpose of assessing the impact of the four independent variables environmental awareness, skin safety awareness, appearance consciousness, word of mouth on the dependent variable that is attitude toward organic cosmetics. The standardized regression coefficients, called beta were used to estimate the effects of each independent variable on the dependent variable. The amount of change in the dependent variable that is associated with a change of one unit in the independent variable is represented by beta coefficient. The relationship between the variables is denoted by sign. If the regression coefficient is positive, then there is a positive relationship between the variables, and if this value is negative, then a negative relationship is there between variables. Here is the summary of the results of the linear regression analysis.

Table – 7.1 : Regression Co-efficient

VARIABLES			
DEPENDENT	INDEPENDENT	BETA	SIGNIFICANCE
Environmental Awareness	Attitude	0.204	0.030
Skin Safety Awareness	Attitude	0.208	0.044
Appearance Awareness	Attitude	-0.031	0.063
Word of Mouth (Interpersonal communication)	Attitude	0.210	0.027

Source: Primary Data

Environmental consciousness is clearly the most important predictor among various factors influencing positively the attitude towards buying organic cosmetics with a beta of 0.204. Environmentally conscious people use products that have a positive impact on the environment welfare that can be one of the reasons of this relation. Hence, the hypothesis H04 namely, Environmental awareness will positively influence attitude toward buying organic cosmetics has been accepted.

The second most significant predictor of attitude toward buying organic cosmetics is skin safety consciousness, with a significance level of 0.044, the reason may be that people are more aware about organic products and their benefits, like glowing healthy skin, no chemicals, anti-aging etc.

Most of the earlier studies also highlighted concerns for one's health as the principal motive for elucidation attitude, intention and purchase of organic food. Today Consumers have become more health conscious and being healthy has become an important criterion for organic purchases. There exists a huge demand internationally for the research and development of anti-aging, UV protective, whitening and extra moisturizing natural skincare products. The trend for anti-aging skin care products is moving towards developing new botanical ingredients and intermediates targeting specific needs, based on discoveries, and advanced technologies. So, according to the results of the study H5 is also accepted. It is found that Skin safety awareness has positively influenced the attitude towards buying organic cosmetics.

The third significant predictor or attitude towards Appearance consciousness with a significance level of 0.063, cannot be statistically shown to have an impact on attitude toward organic cosmetics which highlighted the importance of appearance consciousness as a important factor of consumers' attitudes toward organic personal care products. As a result, appearance consciousness variable is not showing a strong influence, hence H6 is rejected. It is found that Appearance awareness do not positively influence the attitude towards buying organic cosmetics.

The fourth most significant predictor of attitude toward buying organic cosmetics is word of mouth, with a beta of 0.210. The reason of this relationship can be that in India most of the people rely on the information provided by peers, family, relatives etc. So H7 is also accepted. It is found that the Word of mouth will positively influence the attitude towards buying organic cosmetics.

7.Findings

The results of the study are:

- All the 150 sample respondents are female and it is implied that they Purchase of organic cosmetic products based on age, income and occupation.
- Out of 150 respondents 32 per cent of the respondents belong to the age group of less than 20 years. Nearly 23 per cent of the respondents fall under the age group of 20 – 30 years. The respondents 40 -50 years of age constitute 20.67 per cent of the total respondent. The senior respondents are more than 50 years of age which are accounted for 9.33 per cent of the total. It shows the senior people are less interested in using organic cosmetic than the youngsters.
- Out of 150 sample respondents the majority of respondents became aware of the cosmetic brand through advertisements. It is understood from the table that the

advertisement plays a vital role to make aware of the respondents about different cosmetic brands.

- It is clear that the majority (52.67%) of the respondents purchased the cosmetic product from the department store followed by 29.67 per cent of respondents purchased from General Merchant. Another 12.66 per cent of the respondents make their sales promotion technique at departmental stores where the majority of the respondents purchase the cosmetic.
- Since the table value is less than the calculated value, the null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, it may be concluded that there is a significant difference between opinion of the respondents about sales promotion media and the age of the respondents.
- Since the table value is less than the calculated value, the null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, it may be concluded that there is a significant difference between opinion of the respondents about promotion methods and occupation of the respondents.
- As the calculated value is less than the table value and hence the Null hypothesis is accepted. So it is proved that there is no significant difference between opinion of the respondents about brand loyalty and income of the respondents.
- To find out whether there is awareness towards purchase of organic cosmetics. It is found that Environmental awareness will positively influence attitude toward buying organic cosmetics.
- It is found that skin safety awareness has positively influenced attitude toward buying organic cosmetics.
- It is found that appearance awareness do not positively influence the attitude toward buying organic cosmetics.
- It is found that the word of mouth positively influenced the attitude towards buying organic cosmetics.

8. Summary And Conclusion

In the light of foregoing analysis and findings of the study the following practical suggestions are given for the effective promotion and improvement of organic cosmetic market.

- In the study area, the consumers always look for better quality and reasonable price of the product. Therefore, steps are to be taken to maintain and improve the quality and reduce the price so as to avoid shift in the consumer's choice to other substitutes.
- The Study reveals that the majority of the respondents come to know their organic cosmetic brand through advertisement. Therefore, it implies that the advertisement plays vital role in the organic cosmetic market. To increase more awareness among

the consumers, effective and genuine advertisement must be made. The effective advertisement is not only retaining existing consumers but also attracting new customers.

- Most of respondents were not aware of the contest programmes conducted by the company. Therefore, the organic cosmetic companies may make consumer be aware of the contest, because it is considered as one of the cheapest and effective sales promotion methods. So the companies may plan to make the contest simple and easy to understand so that large number of consumers participates in the programme.
- In order to attract the new consumers, it is suggested that the organic cosmetic companies may give free samples or low priced samples in a small pack to consumers. The pack may indicate the usefulness of the product to make proper choice.
- The new organic cosmetic product launching company may concentrate more on the housewives, employees and professional segment for achieving better results.
- In order to satisfy the consumers who are housewives, it is suggested to the organic cosmetic companies that small jar type package may be introduced in the place of poly pack.
- Only less priced products can successfully penetrate the existing market and therefore the launching company may follow penetration-pricing policy.
- Since youngsters, who are susceptible to change, are more in the potential consumer group, steps may be taken by the organic cosmetic companies to attract this group.
- It is essential for the new organic cosmetic product launching companies to convince the buyers and their friends and relatives about the superiority of its new product to enhance their market share.
- Women are to be given awareness through various programmes regarding the use of cosmetic product and the harmful effects on the use of chemical product and its effect on environment, skin and their personal appearance. Nowadays, customers are aware to use the products which are eco-friendly. It should reach all the women whether they are educated or uneducated by conducting awareness programmes through mass media. The sales representatives of cosmetic products should reach the women personally and explain about the cosmetic products through word of mouth and then only the Companies can successfully sell the product and capture the major share in the cosmetic products.

With growing competition at the market place and the need to realize full benefit of promotion, the organic cosmetic marketers must assess and analyze the present situation of the brand in terms of market share, major competitors, and satisfaction of brand users,

non-users and lapsed users. This benchmark should then be related to the market size and the potential estimated. The companies should incorporate creativity into the promotion methods to make the scheme novel, attractive, and challenging from the viewpoint of its target group i.e. consumer. The organic cosmetic marketers should take effective decisions relating to timing and duration of the schemes to be offered, location-wise selection of dealers, and convention of the trade and sales force about the appropriateness of the scheme. Efforts must also be put in to perfect the measurement methodologies, and in conducting researches on aspects like deal prone consumer, incentive scheme and gift selection factors, attitudes of trade and consumers towards the use of promotion schemes. Skin care products are increasingly becoming part of women's daily regimen rather than purely being used on some special occasions. With rapidly changing lifestyles and increase in disposable income in India, consumer preferences are changing. Increasing sales of cosmeceuticals can be associated with rising awareness about using organic products with medicinal proprieties which produces no harms. To strengthen cosmeceuticals manufacturing, more newer and advanced products are introduced by the companies to increase sales. Various skincare products such as herbal face washes, anti-ageing creams, anti-blemishing creams, exfoliates, scrubs, etc., are being launched by international as well as domestic players across the country. Moreover, Indian consumers, especially women have a strong and growing inclination to look young, good and presentable which proves as a drive to boost the industry. The skin care segment accounted for a value share of 20% in India cosmeceutical, cosmetics & personal care market in 2025 and this share is projected to further grow in the coming years, according to Industry Report, Assoc ham India. Therefore, the companies must increase their focus on Organic cosmetic products.

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